

**DIFFERENT ATTITUDE TO IMPROVE LISTENING ABILITY AND SOLUTIONS FOR
PROBLEMS OF LISTENING COMPREHENSION**

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ABSTRACT: This article describes common difficulties that most students facing with listening comprehension, furthermore, shows some strategies that to overcome from these problems. And also aims to provide recommendation and variety of techniques to develop listening skills, as well as, how to improve the ability more successful than expected.

Keywords: Environmental factors, eye contact, depression, cognition, memory games, podcasts, bilingual, accent, learning atmosphere.

In today's globalized world, modern teaching strategies have been developing very rapidly. The use of modern teaching methods will lead to effectiveness if you know how to utilize them with your studies. We know, many students have some problems with listening comprehension due to the following reasons:

- Inability to concentrate while listening;
- Not being able to remember the details;
- The learner's limited vocabulary;
- What is more, lack of control over the speed at which speakers speak and so on.

These are most common conditions that many learners have.

To tackle the problems, firstly, you need all your power of concentration to start, to feel relaxed, also taking a deep breath of fresh air and calming yourself will help you a lot and just try to avoid being distracted by environmental factors. For example, side conversations, sound of pens, trembling legs, these kinds of situations will happen when people start worrying. You can also create your own style to defeat the fear, such as playing with your finger or a pencil which are my keys of increasing focus. Moreover, put aside distracting thought, try to think about the exam that you are going to take. If you have a conversation face-to-face look at the speaker's body directly, because listening the speaker's body movement may shows feelings and thoughts clearly

more than you might think. Eye contact is also very beneficial to gain speaker's attention to you. Feel that you have enough knowledge to pass the exam or calm yourself because you deserve the best. While trouble concentrating can be caused by something as simple as stress or lack of sleep, it can also be a symptom of depression or anxiety. Your focus is very dependent on many physical and mental factors too and some are good for your focus, others are not. Get enough sleep as much as your body needs, if you don't sleep sufficiently, your focus and judgment suffers, you may feel tiredness and lack of energy all day long. Sleeping and being relaxed all the time are one of the great secrets of good concentration. Also, the types of food we eat ought to be full of nutrition, protein and exercising or taking a walk to nature, talking with your loved ones, significantly impacts your ability to stay focused. Studies show, eating bananas help students learn more effectively and improve exam results. To train your brain, playing certain types of games can help you get better at concentrating. However, some brain games may not be the only type of game that can help improve concentration, you may only feel tired. Organizing your day, for example, having a plan the night before or writing down your plans that must get completed in order for that day to be productive and relieving stress.

Secondly, after listening you may find it almost impossible to retain some information acquired. Memory and other thinking problems have many possible causes, including depression, an infection, or medication side effects. Sometimes, the problem can be treated, and cognition improves. And one of the certain causes of not to remember the details are not paying attention while listening and not focusing to the task. By more exercising, step by step, you will learn how to keep tracking on speech and to select the correct answer while you are listening. From my experience, writing down the podcasts word by word to a paper was really advantageous, to improve my memory and comprehension. As well as, you can also type the listening tests that you had, by writing down and listening again you will increase your memory and learn new vocabulary, Moreover you will start to understand easily. Including physical activity, memory games in your daily routine such as playing cards, Crosswords, Sudoku and other puzzles are an easy way to build a stronger mind. You consume healthy foods to have stronger your mind. Berries, fish, and leafy green vegetables are the best foods that fight memory loss. There is mountain of evidence showing they support and protect brain cells. Also, eggs offer a host of healthy nutrients.

As far as, brain health goes, egg source of chlorine, which is associated with reducing inflammation and promoting brain function, like maintaining memory and communications between brain cells.

Most students acquire vocabulary incidentally through indirect exposure to words at home and communicating with people by listening and talking, as well as, reading aloud and widely on their own. The amount of reading is important to long-term vocabulary development. Having strong vocabulary foundation is very useful while you are doing listening tests. For improving your vocabulary, first, you ought to learn at least ten or twenty new words a day, not just by memorizing it, instead, by writing examples for each of them, second, use them on a daily basis, reflect them on your conversations. You can easily find the answer to each and every question, in other words, understanding exactly what they really mean if you have core vocabulary bases. Another simple way of learning new words is vocabulary tests and word games; learning new vocabulary by playing games is more enjoyable. In some cases, if you do not know meaning of the word, you can try to answer it from context. Learning how to guess correctly is also very efficacious when you face the condition that you are not sure whether you will be correct. As we just mentioned above, by writing down podcasts or listening tests, you can also familiar with new words easily. With appropriate more strategies, you will have built up listening skill by the time. Some people say “if you able to speak two languages equally well, you are the bilingual person and if you start to forget the words and not learning new ones, it should be “dyinglingual” ”. So, by saying that “Never settle!”

In fact, some students may miss the line while they are doing listening tests. These difficulties may be from speaker’s speed, accent, pronunciation, and grammar structures, in my opinion. As a second language for any people, the speed might be problem for new learners, first. But if, the training keeps hard work in long hours, it will become easier. The time you spent, teaching and practicing active listening strategies always beneficial in enhancing listening comprehension. Furthermore, one of the biggest challenges to overcome is understanding speaker’s accent and pronunciation. There are many native accents: British, Australian, New Zealand, American, and Canadian. These countries accent is vary differently from each other. This can often provide challenges for students who are still learning pronunciation between nations. That is why, decide which accent you want to imitate, after some time you able to distinguish the other accents, too.

Finding native speakers as a friend and having conversation as much as you can will show great impact on your language learning process. Most of students that I know, improved their listening and speaking skill by watching variety of films and listening music. Because, you will be familiar lots of new vocabulary and grammar structures for understanding easily.

Choosing a teacher and textbook for improving listening comprehension plays a big role, too. To improve your listening skills find the technique that you prefer to learn most, make it fun and fruitful learning atmosphere for yourself.

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